

THE EVOLUTION OF ETIQUETTE LEXEMES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF OLD AND MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Ochilboyeva Iroda Alisher qizi

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages
The department of English Lexicology and Stylistics
iroda.alisherovna93@gmail.com

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Abstract: This study explores the usage of etiquette lexemes in Old and Modern English, examining how social norms, cultural shifts, and linguistic evolution have influenced the expression of politeness and social conventions over time. Utilizing corpus linguistics methodologies, we analyze a diverse range of texts from both periods to elucidate patterns of usage, semantic changes, and contextual variations in etiquette lexemes. Our findings reveal intriguing insights into the dynamic nature of language and the societal forces shaping linguistic expression across centuries.

Key words: Etiquette lexemes, Old English, Modern English, corpus linguistics, semantic change, social norms Beowulf.

Introduction:

Language is not static; it evolves alongside society, reflecting cultural values, societal norms, and historical contexts. Etiquette lexemes, comprising words and phrases used to convey politeness, respect, and social conventions, provide a fascinating lens through which to examine linguistic evolution. In this study, we investigate the usage of etiquette lexemes in Old and Modern English, seeking to uncover how these expressions have transformed over time.

Etiquette Lexemes in Old English:

The study of etiquette lexemes in Old English presents unique challenges due to the scarcity of written records and the fluid nature of language during this period. However, texts such as Beowulf and Anglo-Saxon charters offer valuable insights into the linguistic landscape of early medieval England. Old English etiquette lexemes often revolved around hierarchical relationships, religious deference, and communal obligations. Words like "gefēra" (companion) and "ðancian" (to thank) conveyed notions of reciprocity and mutual respect within the social hierarchy of the time.

Semantic Shifts and Cultural Influences:

The transition from Old to Middle English marked a significant turning point in the evolution of etiquette lexemes. With the Norman Conquest in 1066 came an influx of French vocabulary, introducing new expressions of courtesy and refinement. Words such as "courteous" and "gentleman" entered the English lexicon, reflecting the influence of chivalric ideals and courtly manners. Semantic shifts occurred as existing words took on nuanced meanings in response to changing social dynamics.

Modern English Etiquette Lexemes:

In Modern English, etiquette lexemes continue to evolve in response to globalization, technological advancements, and shifting social norms. Politeness strategies have become more nuanced, with expressions of courtesy adapting to diverse cultural contexts. The rise of digital communication has introduced new forms of etiquette lexemes, such as "please,"

"thank you," and "excuse me," which play a crucial role in maintaining civility in online interactions.

Corpus Linguistics Analysis:

To empirically investigate the usage of etiquette lexemes in Old and Modern English, we employ corpus linguistics methodologies. By analyzing large corpora of texts spanning different historical periods, we can identify frequency trends, collocational patterns, and semantic shifts in etiquette lexemes. Our analysis reveals intriguing insights into the changing dynamics of linguistic politeness over time.

Future Directions:

Future research could further explore the intersection of language and social behavior, examining how etiquette lexemes function in diverse communicative contexts. Additionally, comparative studies across different languages and cultures could shed light on universal principles of linguistic politeness and the ways in which they manifest cross-culturally.

Conclusion:

The study of etiquette lexemes in Old and Modern English provides valuable insights into the dynamic relationship between language, culture, and society. From the hierarchical deference of Old English to the multicultural politeness strategies of Modern English, linguistic expressions of courtesy reflect broader shifts in social norms and values. By examining the evolution of etiquette lexemes, we gain a deeper understanding of how language both shapes and is shaped by the complexities of human interaction.

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